

**HYGROTHERMAL INFLUENCE ON THE INTERLAMINAR
FRACTURE ENERGY OF GRAPHITE/BISMALEIMIDE
MODIFIED EPOXY COMPOSITE (IM6/5245C)**

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ABSTRACT

Moisture diffusion properties of graphite/bismaleimide (IM6/5245C) were determined and used for predictions of realistic moisture weight gains in aircraft application. Double cantilever beam test specimens were tested both dry and wet at -50°C , 22°C , 80°C and 120°C . Wet specimens were preconditioned to the predicted moisture levels. IM6/5245C did not demonstrate any improvement in toughness based on G_I values over a standard epoxy system (AS1/3501-6). IM6/5245C also seems to be sensitive to combined influence of moisture and temperature at both low and high temperature extremes.

INTRODUCTION

Current graphite fibre-reinforced epoxies such as T300/5208 and AS/3501 have relatively poor post-impact performance and are environmentally sensitive. Thus, because of the necessity of preventing growth of impact-induced damage under service loads, it is usual to impose a design limit of 4000 microstrain. Unfortunately, this means that the design strain levels at which these materials are utilized are significantly below their potential in the undamaged state. Significant weight savings over current composite designs could be achieved in aircraft structures if higher strain levels were to be allowed.

Such considerations have prompted the development of new high-strain graphite fibres and tougher, high glass transition temperature resins. One such material is IM6/5245C fabricated by Narmco. IM6 is a high-strain graphite fibre while the resin is a blend of epoxy and bismaleimide and is described as a bismaleimide-modified-epoxy.

According to manufacturers data(1), 5245C resin has excellent "hot-wet" properties at 130 to 150°C (270-300°F) and has high impact resistance (toughness). The Narmco data looked promising and in fact several aircraft manufacturers in Canada and elsewhere are considering this material in their programs. The Structures and Materials Laboratory has performed characterization tests to compare this material with other materials of the same class and these data are being published separately. Narmco, in their data bulletin, reported the results of characterization tests after a 40 hour "boil" pre-soak cycle. These results cannot be regarded as indicative of the material performance characteristics in the aircraft application since moisture gains and diffusion properties were not reported.

In this paper, limited diffusion property data for IM6/5245C are presented along with realistic service predictions for the worst-anticipated climate and aircraft utilization scenarios for fighter-type aircraft.

Realistic levels of moisture uptake and through the thickness distribution have to be used in the characterization testing of the resin matrix composites. Excessively high moisture levels, easily obtained in a laboratory using processes such as boiling or high temperature/high humidity presoaking, may severely reduce composite mechanical properties. The necessity for realism in environmental testing was indicated in a literature review(2-5).

The environmental sensitivity of a composite system can be assessed in tests which measure matrix dependent properties. As environmental tests of composites are generally expensive and difficult to perform, the Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) test which directly measures the resistance to mode I interlaminar fracture, was chosen as a first test to give an indication of environmental sensitivity of the IM6/5245C system. The DCB test has been used widely to measure the mode I energy release rate. This paper presents results of DCB tests performed at various temperatures on both dry and wet specimens which were conditioned to represent the worst-anticipated moisture levels.

Diffusion Properties Measurement

Specimens manufactured from IM6/5245C were exposed to various combinations of temperature and humidity. The 22°C and 65°C moisture

Figure 1 Weight gain vs time.

Figure 2 Weight gain vs time.

weight gains were of the type shown in Figure 1 and it was found that they could be approximated using Fick's model of moisture diffusion (continuous lines in Fig. 1).

The 80°C weight gain is shown in Figure 2. Similar moisture uptake at extreme conditions was observed for T300/5208(6) and for an anhydride-cured epoxy(7) and generally indicated decomposition of the resin system. Further testing will be required to determine the cause of this behaviour and whether this exposure caused irreversible damage to the IM6/5245C composite.

The diffusion data for IM6/5245C can be found in(8).

Long Term Predictions

The environmental and flight profile input as well as the computer code is described more extensively elsewhere(9,10). Here, only some results will be shown: Figure 3 presents weight gain in an 18 ply IM6/5245C laminate under worst case aircraft storage conditions only and under combined fighter usage and storage conditions. The lack of significant difference is striking. The fighter profile contained a high

Figure 3 Weight gain predictions.

temperature "spike" which was expected to lower the long term equilibrium moisture level. The reason for the absence of a large drying effect is that drying due to the thermal "spike" is balanced by a much higher diffusivity of the bismaleimide modified epoxy compared to standard epoxy resins such as 3501-5(9). It is also significant that the stable level, around which the

moisture level oscillates slightly due to seasonal climatic changes, is reached practically within the first year of exposure, much faster than in standard epoxy systems(9). This worst case moisture level for the IM6/5245C is slightly below 0.7% weight gain as evident in Figure 3.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

DCB specimens containing an artificial delamination defect were prepared from the unidirectional 18-ply panels. Artificial delaminations of various sizes were introduced during the lay-up process by inserting a 0.076mm thick piece of Teflon of different lengths into each panel at the mid-thickness. These panels were subsequently cured in an autoclave. A Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) test showed that the panels were fully cured. The glass transition temperature (T_g) of 200°C was determined by a Thermomechanical Analysis (TMA). The panels were C-scanned and were found to be free of detectable defects. Following the quality inspections, which indicated good quality of the panels, the 2.5mm thick panels were cut into specimens 254mm long by 38.1mm wide. Hinged metal end tabs were bolted on one end of the specimen for the application of the load (as per NASA Reference Publication(11)).

The specimens were tested under displacement control using an MTS servo-hydraulic testing machine and an environmental chamber. A

displacement rate of 0.075mm/s was used. Tests were conducted at 4 different temperatures (-50°C, 22°C, 80°C, 120°C) with specimens in either the dry condition or pre-conditioned to the worst case moisture level of 0.7%. The applied displacement (δ) and the corresponding load (P) were continuously recorded on an X-Y plotter and simultaneously stored using an IBM-PC/HP3497A data acquisition system.

The applied displacement was increased until a change in specimen compliance corresponding to an approximate 10mm crack extension was observed. The displacement was held constant until the load stabilized and then the load was decreased to zero load and the specimen removed from the load frame/chamber for crack front position measurement. The specimen was loaded to approximately 50% of the last crack arrest load and then the crack front was measured on both sides of the specimen using travelling microscopes. The average of these two very close values was used as the crack length. The specimen was then returned to the load frame. The actuator displacement had to be re-zeroed each time as every crack extension resulted in a slight (less than 2mm) permanent opening deflection of the specimen. Adequate time was allowed for the specimen temperature to stabilize. This period of time was previously determined by inserting a thermocouple between the two mid-plyes of a tightly closed specimen placed in the chamber. The entire loading/unloading process was repeated five times for each specimen during which the total moisture loss varied from 0.02 to 0.1% depending on the temperature. It is expected that most of this loss is from the outer layers and that the moisture loss in mid layers is less significant.

One specimen of each condition was maintained in an opened state following the last crack extension so that the interlaminar fracture surfaces remained undisturbed for post-failure examination using a scanning electron microscope.

RESULTS

A typical load-displacement plot obtained is shown in Figure 4. The five consecutive load/unload loops are shifted 5mm horizontally. The first load loop was to extend the crack front beyond the Teflon insert to create a natural crack for the next measurement.

Figure 4 Typical load-displacement curves.

Figure 5 Temperature effect on load-displacement curves (dry DCB tests).

Figure 6 Temperature effect on load-displacement curves (wet DCB tests).

Figures 5 and 6 show typical load-displacement loops for dry and wet specimens at various temperatures. For these figures the first "break-in" test was omitted and consecutive load/unload cycles were plotted without shifting. For clarity, only the first and last linear portions of load vs displacement loops are plotted. For dry specimens at 22°C, 80°C and 120°C, the crack growth was stable and the loads increased slightly with temperature. The -50°C dry specimens demonstrated linear load-displacement behaviour up to the point where a small unstable crack extension was observed as evidenced in the plot by a rapid drop in load. The serrated curve was also observed in the cold-wet tests (Fig. 6) with much more accentuated serrations than in the dry state.

The inclusion of moisture had a dramatic effect on crack extension loads. Compared with the dry tests, the loads were

lower in the -50°C tests, almost the same at 22°C , higher at 80°C and at times nearly 100% higher at 120°C . The crack extension at 120°C was often unstable resulting in a large drop in load. Unlike the cold tests this unstable growth is preceded by slow crack growth during which the load also increases.

A visual study of the fracture surfaces showed that the regions with spontaneous crack growth are darker than the regions of slow crack growth. Moreover, the number of these darker regions corresponds exactly to the number of drops in load. The phenomenon of spontaneous crack growth in wet specimens has been previously observed by Garg and Ishai(12).

It should be noted that little or no fiber bridging was observed in the cold test specimens. The amount of fibre bridging increased with temperature, and was very significant in the hot-wet tests at both 80°C and 120°C . At 120°C the crack-front measurement was made difficult by the appearance of cracks in adjacent interply layers.

The assumption of linear elastic response of DCB specimens has been used frequently and here also the calculations of energy release rate are based on the general equation:

$$G = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (1)$$

where P is load, b is specimen width, a is crack length and C is the compliance of the DCB specimen δ/P . Exponential curves of the form $C = Ra^n$ were used to fit the compliance versus crack length data (Berry's method(13)). Minor data scatter was observed in the typical compliance versus crack length plots. As expected, these plots were essentially the same for all the different hygrothermal conditions; the differences were within the scatter. The cantilever beam compliance is basically a fibre dominated property and is therefore practically insensitive to moisture and temperature variations within the range used in this work.

Strain energy release rates (G) were calculated using the crack arrest load. This approach gives lower, conservative values of G than does crack initiation load. Also, the crack initiation load is, in some instances, an arbitrary value.

Strain energy release rates versus crack length were plotted for each condition. No influence of Teflon insert length was observed. The first G value for each specimen was considerably lower than the values for longer cracks. This trend was apparent in most tests except those at -50°C where the G value did not show significant increase with crack growth.

The SEM observations of the fracture surfaces were made using one specimen from each test condition. A typical fracture surface is presented in Figure 7. Both matrix and interfacial failures were

Figure 7 SEM of typical fracture surface.

Figure 8 SEM of -50°C wet fracture surface.

observed. The region adjacent to the Teflon insert was different in that the fracture surface was a smooth through the matrix failure. A similar feature was also observed for the whole crack surface in -50°C wet specimen (Fig. 8).

DISCUSSION

The SEM observations support the view that the G values for short (5 to 10mm) crack extensions beyond the Teflon starter are the critical G_{I} values for the matrix. The higher G values obtained for longer crack extensions represent combined release rate energies in the resin,

interface and fibers as evidenced by SEM and fiber bridging observations. A similar interpretation of DCB tests was suggested by other authors notably Russell and Street(14). More recently Johnson and Mangalgiri(15) showed that G_I obtained using a thin layer of matrix between two aluminum beams corresponded to the initial G_I value from a DCB test of composite material using the same matrix.

The critical energy release rate G_I for the matrix is shown plotted against temperature in Figure 9. Within the -50°C to 80°C range the

Figure 9 Plots of G_{Im} vs temperature.

evident already during this stage of crack propagation. This would suggest that a large plastic zone is present around the crack tip. It seems that moisture has a dramatic plasticizing effect on the matrix at this temperature.

Russell and Street have used DCB specimens to measure G_I in AS1/3501-6(14). They used both dry and wet specimens and tested them at temperatures of -50°C , 20°C and 100°C . They used specimens 8, 16 and 24 plies thick and found no influence of thickness on G_I values for the matrix. Their cross-head displacement rate was 0.042mm/s versus 0.075mm/s used here. This is not a significant difference in light of the results published by Aliyu and Daniel(16). The preconditioning scheme employed by Russell and Street is thought to be unrepresentative since nonuniform moisture distributions were present in the specimens and

differences due to moisture and temperature are within the scatter. There is significant increase in energy release rate in wet specimens at 120°C . This value cannot, however, be treated as matrix G_I as cracks in adjacent plies have appeared before the crack progressed beyond the Teflon insert and fibre bridging was

it is suspected that the moisture content in mid layers was below the worst levels that could be obtained in an aircraft application. The Russell and Street AS1/3501-6 data are plotted against IM6/5245C in Figure 9. While wet tests should not be compared, the dry tests did not demonstrate superior toughness of IM6/5245C over AS1/3501-6(14) (standard epoxy system). This result should not be surprising as bismaleimides are known to be brittle(17).

Figure 10 Plots of G combined vs temperature.

temperature and moisture should be further investigated using other tests.

For most of the conditions tested, the combined G for longer cracks is higher than the G_{mI} seen in the crack initiation stage. This provides some measure of safety if the G_{mI} values are used in calculations. However, it is important to note that in wet -50°C conditions other fracture energy release rates did not manifest themselves and the crack continued to progress at lower loads than in the dry specimens.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Moisture weight gains in "wet" tests should be monitored and realistic weight gains should be utilized as excessive moisture

The G combined is a function of G_{mI} , G_{mIII} , G_{iI} , G_{iIII} where subscripts i and m indicate interface and matrix respectively(18). While G_{mI} seems to exhibit little sensitivity to the environmental conditions used (Fig. 9), the other modes are sensitive as can be seen in Figure 10. This sensitivity of IM6/5245C to both

levels and non representative through thickness distributions can be attained by accelerated laboratory preconditioning.

2. The IM6/5245C does not seem to be tougher than AS1/3501-6, a standard epoxy system, under the environmental and testing conditions employed in this study.
3. Further testing should be undertaken to verify whether the effect of temperature and moisture will have significant impact on other IM6/5245C properties (compression, shear, transverse tension, etc.).
4. Moisture may have significant effect on delamination extension at low temperatures.
5. DCB test indicated a significant plasticizing effect of combined temperature and moisture on 5245C at 80°C and 120°C.

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